

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D6.1 Project website and social media presence

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Contributors and Peer Reviewers

Contributors
Vasileios Machamint (EBOS)
Peer Reviewers
Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Christina Lessi (OTE)

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs	8
1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	9
2 Project Website	10
2.1 Methodology for website construction and development	10
2.2 Website Content	12
2.2.1 Website Structure	12
2.2.2 Home Page	13
2.2.3 The 'About' Page	16
2.2.4 The 'Concept and Methodology' Page	17
2.2.5 The 'Objectives' Page	18
2.2.6 The 'Target Use Cases' page	19
2.2.7 The 'Consortium' Page	20
2.2.8 The 'Dissemination & Communication' Page	21
2.2.9 The 'News & Events' Page	22
2.2.10 Website Content Update Process	22
2.3 Privacy Policy and Cookies Policy	23
2.4 Google Analytics Website Traffic	24
2.5 Website Administration	26
3 Social Media Channels	27
3.1 VITAL-5G LinkedIn account	27
3.2 VITAL-5G Twitter account	28
3.3 VITAL-5G YouTube account	29
4 Conclusions	30
5 References	31

List of Figures

Figure 1: VITAL-5G Website – Smartphone View	11
Figure 2: Structure of VITAL-5G website	12
Figure 3: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (1/4)	13
Figure 4: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (2/4)	14
Figure 5: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (3/4)	14
Figure 6: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (4/4)	15
Figure 7: VITAL-5G Website - About Page (1/2)	16
Figure 8: VITAL-5G Website - About Page (2/2)	16
Figure 9: VITAL-5G Website – Concept and Methodology Page	17
Figure 10: VITAL-5G Website – Objectives Page	18
Figure 11: VITAL-5G Website – Target Use Cases Page.....	19
Figure 12: VITAL-5G Website – Consortium Page	20
Figure 13: VITAL-5G Website – Dissemination & Communication Page	21
Figure 14: VITAL-5G Website – News & Events Page	22
Figure 15: VITAL-5G Website – Accept Cookies	23
Figure 16: VITAL-5G Website – Change Cookie Settings	23
Figure 17: VITAL-5G Google Analytics (1/2)	24
Figure 18: VITAL-5G Google Analytics (2/2)	25
Figure 19: VITAL-5G LinkedIn Page.....	27
Figure 20: VITAL-5G Twitter Page	28
Figure 21: VITAL-5G YouTube Page	29

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	8
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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
DoA	Description of the Action
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	EU General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document establishes VITAL-5G's website, and associated social media channels, providing initial material to support internal and external communication activities. The description and analysis include the methodology behind the design and the implementation of a powerful, modern and user-friendly website with multi-browser and multi-device compatibility. The first version of the website is ready and publicly available at <https://www.vital5g.eu/>.

Moreover, the administration of the website is also described in this document, along with Google Analytics presenting the website's traffic.

Access to the social media accounts is also provided through this document. LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube accounts have already been setup and are accessible via the following links but also via the project website.

- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vital-5g-project/>
- <https://twitter.com/5gVital>
- <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYVsDTKWFAhijxyTZ5H3Uwg>

The content of the website will be continuously updated with dissemination material (i.e., newsletters, publications, results, etc.) until the completion of the Project.

1 Introduction

The Deliverable ‘D6.1 Project website and social media presence’ of the VITAL-5G project is part of Work Package (WP) 6 ‘Dissemination, Communication & Standardisation’. It refers to the construction and publishing of the project’s official website itself and the setup of other social media channels, such as LinkedIn¹ Twitter² and YouTube³. This document is a supplementary companion report accompanying the deliverable D6.1, which is a type “other” deliverable. The report accompanies the actual deliverables of the website and the social media presence, providing an overview and key information about them.

The deliverable is of significant importance since it marks from an early stage the “online” dissemination activity and the initial web presence and visibility of VITAL-5G project. The first website version was set-up and launched during M1 (January 2021) and is continuously updated. These updates will continue until the end of the project.

To support knowledge dissemination and impact creation, all public deliverables will be published on the project website.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 6.1 – Dissemination & communication activities	This task will set up and maintain the project website by month M02 (by EBOS), which will address a wide and versatile community and will be updated regularly. The portal will be complemented by a social media communication strategy and channels (e.g., LinkedIn groups, Facebook) that will ensure a broad diffusion of the project results and promote the project in online discussion communities.	Chapter 2- Project Website Chapter 3 - Social Media channels	The deliverable describes the visual identity of the project in detail, such as the logo, the website and the social media channels created. Therefore, in this deliverable the reader will find: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description and screenshots from VITAL-5G website. • Description and screenshots from VITAL-5G’s social networks. • Methodology followed during the website design and implementation. • The administration of the website.
DELIVERABLE			
D6.1: Project website and social media presence			

¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/>

² <https://twitter.com/>

³ <https://twitter.com/>

Delivery of the operational project website and social media accounts.

Delivery of this accompanying report.

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The Deliverable consists of 4 Chapters.

Chapter 1 presents the introduction of the document.

Chapter 2 delivers a wide-ranging picture of the project website including the development methodology used along with the content and screenshots of each page. Moreover, Chapter 2 provides some Google Analytics results for the website along with a description of how the administration of the website can be performed (*i.e.*, update content, add-remove pages, *etc.*) and some details about the privacy and cookies policy of this website.

Chapter 3 provides information about the social media accounts of the project (LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube) and presents some screenshots of these accounts.

Finally, in Chapter 4, the conclusions of the document are provided.

2 Project Website

This Chapter describes in detail the VITAL-5G website that has been developed to serve as the public presence of the Project. It is a website that utilizes the latest technology in order to deliver content rich information to the visitor of the site. The VITAL website is part of the dissemination activities undertaken for this project. The Project website can be accessed using the following internet address <https://www.vital5g.eu/>.

2.1 Methodology for website construction and development

For implementing the VITAL-5G official website, user interface design principles and GA requirements have been taken into consideration. VITAL-5G's modern interface embeds the latest best practices in its design to achieve multi-browser and multi-device compatibility. Its interface is fully reactive, user-friendly, delivering content rich information to the visitor. That means that the user can access the VITAL-5G website from a smartphone, tablet, desktop PC or laptop and have easy access to any content. Both the design and implementation process follow a user-centred implementation, building an interface that is well-organized, practical and easy to use.

The following GUI Design Principles [1] were adopted in the VITAL-5G website interface design and implementation:

- **Clarity:** The interface is visually, conceptually, and linguistically clear.
- **Comprehensibility:** The interface is intuitive, and the flow is easy to learn.
- **Consistency:** The interface looks, acts, and operates in a consistent manner.
- **Control:** The user controls the interaction, and in particular:
 - Actions result from explicit user requests.
 - Actions are performed quickly.
 - Actions can be interrupted or terminated.
 - The user is never interrupted by errors.
- **Efficiency:**
 - The design minimises user's eye and hand movements.
 - Transitions between various system controls flow easily and freely.
 - Navigation paths are as short as possible.
- **Simplicity:**
 - Provide as simple interface as possible.
 - Common actions are made simple.
 - Uniformity and consistency are provided throughout the website.

HTML5 [2], CSS3 [3], and JavaScript [4] technologies have been adopted during the implementation of the VITAL-5G website, to achieve a responsive result, cross browser functionality and multi device compatibility. Figure 1 below presents the mobile version of the website.

Figure 1: VITAL-5G Website – Smartphone View

The website has been developed to serve as the main dissemination platform for reaching interested stakeholders. All sections of the website have the VITAL-5G logo at the top and the acknowledgement of funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme at the bottom of the page, where the EU emblem (EU flag) is displayed together with the text referring the programme and the number of the grant agreement, in line with the requirements of the European Commission. The project website:

- Presents the VITAL-5G project and provides a general overview of the project,
- Presents the specific objectives of the project,
- Describes the system that will be deployed and also the results and barriers to overcome,
- Aims to recruit additional interested stakeholders,
- elaborates on the news and results of the VITAL-5G project, by sharing the project progress calendar of events, and interim and final public documents/deliverables.
- Provides an easy to access communication channel to all project participants via the *Contact Us* section

2.2 Website Content

This subsection provides information about the website content and its update process. At this early stage in the project only the generic pages describing the objectives, concept, methodology and use cases of the project and the consortium overview are populated. As soon as they are available, additional publications and non-confidential deliverables will be added on the website. Furthermore, the Website Content Process is briefly described.

2.2.1 Website Structure

Figure 2 shows in a diagram the sitemap of the initial working version of VITAL-5G website:

Figure 2: Structure of VITAL-5G website

2.2.2 Home Page

The 'Home page' of the VITAL-5G website is the first one loaded when a user opens the website in a web browser, based on the rationale of long-scrolling pages, so as to give website visitors an early experience of the website's contents.

Figure 3 - Figure 6 show several screenshots from the 'Home page' of the website. By scrolling down the Home Page, the visitor can see the complete title of the project, a short description of the project, the main objectives, the news, the consortium, and some contact details.

The header hosts the main navigation menu, as well as links to social media channels of the VITAL-5G Project. The main navigation menu is consistently placed through all webpages, while the project logo also acts as a redirection to the home page.

Figure 3: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (1/4)

Objectives

<p style="text-align: center;">1</p> <p>To drive and foster the development and sharing of novel vertical-specific and vertical-agnostic Network Applications (NetApps) for the T&L sector by supporting open source tools and an open repository for flexible and interoperable deployment through the VITAL-5G platform.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">2</p> <p>To deliver an open, virtualized 5G-enabled testing and validation experimentation facility, which will provide the means for relevant T&L stakeholders to deploy and benchmark the performance of their innovative NetApps on top of a 5G network.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">3</p> <p>To demonstrate the benefit and showcase the added value of 5G connectivity for advanced multi-modal logistics services across European roads, seas and rivers, creating a functional value chain for highly automated freight transportation.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">4</p> <p>To provide customized and virtualized access to network and T&L infrastructure (port, warehouse, equipment and facilities) resources, enabling dynamic tailor-made service provisioning to 3rd parties (such as SMEs) to validate their applications over resources otherwise unavailable to them, thus boosting confidence prior to actual service deployment.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">5</p> <p>To enable novel business models development for open, integrated and cooperative services across multiple domains, addressing specific T&L use cases and to justify the investment from key stakeholders.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">6</p> <p>To foster the development and advancement of a T&L centred ecosystem, which will drive the European integration of 5G services into the T&L vertical, by bringing together key vertical stakeholders (port authorities, road operators, MNOs, etc.) with SMEs developing cutting-edge technology and applications.</p>

Figure 4: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (2/4)

News & Events

NEW H2020 ICT-41 5G PROJECT VITAL-5G KICKS OFF!

On the 26th and 27th of January 2021, the new 5G Research and Innovation project VITAL-5G Project "Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities" held a successful online kick-off meeting with the participation of partners and the coordination of WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS. VITAL-5G is part of 5G PPP Phase 3 and will ...

[Read More »](#)

[Read all](#)

Project Coordinated by:

Consortium:

Figure 5: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (3/4)

Figure 6: VITAL-5G Website - Home Page (4/4)

2.2.3 The 'About' Page

The 'About' page, includes a short description of the project (Figure 7Figure 8). It is noted that the 'About' menu is a drop-down list, including also options leading to other subpages regarding the Concept and Methodology, the Project Objectives, the Targeted Use Cases and the Consortium of the project. All information is in alignment with the VITAL-5G Description of Action (DoA).

Figure 7: VITAL-5G Website - About Page (1/2)

Figure 8: VITAL-5G Website - About Page (2/2)

2.2.4 The ‘Concept and Methodology’ Page

The ‘Concept and Methodology’ page gives an overview of the concept and the methodology of the project stemming from the DoA (as shown in Figure 9).

Shown below are the vertical-agnostic NetApps which will serve general purpose functionalities which can be utilized by multiple participating parties in a variety of vertical use cases.

- » VS1: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing
- » VS2: Remote inspection & risk assessment
- » VS3: IoT Management platform
- » VS4: Real time digital twin
- » VS5: Data stream organization

Figure 9: VITAL-5G Website – Concept and Methodology Page

2.2.5 The 'Objectives' Page

On the 'Objectives' page (Figure 10), the visitor can find the main six objectives that the project will focus on according to the DoA.

Objectives

- » **Objective 1:** To drive and foster the development and sharing of novel vertical-specific and vertical-agnostic Network Applications (NetApps) for the T&L sector by supporting open source tools and an open repository for flexible and interoperable deployment through the VITAL-5G platform.
- » **Objective 2:** To deliver an open, virtualized 5G-enabled testing and validation experimentation facility, which will provide the means for relevant T&L stakeholders to deploy and benchmark the performance of their innovative NetApps on top of a 5G network.
- » **Objective 3:** To demonstrate the benefit and showcase the added value of 5G connectivity for advanced multi-modal logistics services across European roads, seas and rivers, creating a functional value chain for highly automated freight transportation.
- » **Objective 4:** To provide customized and virtualized access to network and T&L infrastructure (port, warehouse, equipment and facilities) resources, enabling dynamic tailor-made service provisioning to 3rd parties (such as SMEs) to validate their applications over resources otherwise unavailable to them, thus boosting confidence prior to actual service deployment.
- » **Objective 5:** To enable novel business models development for open, integrated and cooperative services across multiple domains, addressing specific T&L use cases and to justify the investment from key stakeholders.
- » **Objective 6:** To foster the development and advancement of a T&L centred ecosystem, which will drive the European integration of 5G services into the T&L vertical, by bringing together key vertical stakeholders (port authorities, road operators, MNOs, etc.) with SMEs developing cutting-edge technology and applications. To accelerate the adoption and scale-up of VITAL-5G experimentation facility and NetApps through wide dissemination means and provide contributions to key standardisation organisations.

Site Links

[Home](#)
[About](#)

Follow Us

The strategic objective of VITAL-5G is to create an open, virtualized

Dissemination & Communication

Figure 10: VITAL-5G Website – Objectives Page

2.2.6 The ‘Target Use Cases’ page

The “Target Use Cases” page provides relevant information about VITAL-5G’s Use Cases, focusing on the problem definition and addressed challenges, the targeted Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the main functionalities to be developed for each of them within the context of the project. An indicative screenshot of the Target use case page, providing a figure and information about the use case, is shown in

Each time a vessel enters the port reach, new instances of T&L NetApp are created (e.g. one instance of on-board data collection & interfacing for vessels’ NetApps and one instance of the Remote vessel navigation NetApp). Additionally, in order to ensure low latency communication (e.g., to enable quasi-real-time user experience), some instances may run on the edge, and continuous NetApp allocation/reallocation in the different network edges is expected. For that reason, fast service creation times from 5G are required. In terms of 5G communication, 5G URLLC capabilities are mandatory for a dependable functioning of the most critical NetApps (e.g., Remote vessel navigation).

Figure 11.

Each time a vessel enters the port reach, new instances of T&L NetApp are created (e.g. one instance of on-board data collection & interfacing for vessels’ NetApps and one instance of the Remote vessel navigation NetApp). Additionally, in order to ensure low latency communication (e.g., to enable quasi-real-time user experience), some instances may run on the edge, and continuous NetApp allocation/reallocation in the different network edges is expected. For that reason, fast service creation times from 5G are required. In terms of 5G communication, 5G URLLC capabilities are mandatory for a dependable functioning of the most critical NetApps (e.g., Remote vessel navigation).

Figure 11: VITAL-5G Website – Target Use Cases Page

2.2.7 The ‘Consortium’ Page

The ‘Consortium’ page (Figure 12) provides information about the Consortium and briefly presents all partners of the VITAL-5G Project. For each partner, the logo is presented along with each organization’s name. The partners' logos are clickable links, redirecting the user to the partner’s website when clicked.

Figure 12: VITAL-5G Website – Consortium Page

2.2.8 The 'Dissemination & Communication' Page

The 'Dissemination & Communication' page (shown in Figure 13) includes all of the on-going dissemination and communication tools and channels the consortium will be using for disseminating VITAL-5G and its results, namely:

- i. Public Deliverables
- ii. Conferences, Workshops & Congresses
- iii. Publications
- iv. Industry focused events
- v. Brochures & Posters
- vi. Newsletters

The content of these pages will be updated during the project, with the pertinent dissemination material as soon as it is produced.

Figure 13: VITAL-5G Website – Dissemination & Communication Page

2.2.9 The ‘News & Events’ Page

Under this page, the visitor can see all the news about the project, the important meetings etc. This section of the website will be constantly updated according to the activities of the project partners. A screenshot of the page is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: VITAL-5G Website – News & Events Page

2.2.10 Website Content Update Process

The website will be a key enabler for communications between project partners, stakeholders and the wider public and will be continuously updated, adjusted and improved during the project. The website content will be constantly updated with material such as public deliverables, newsletters, news, upcoming meetings, participations in events, dissemination actions, conferences, publications, whitepapers, photos etc.

The website content will be updated regularly based on the communication and dissemination plan driven by WP6. The content updates will be produced mainly as part of WP6, stemming from the activities and procedures of Task 6.1 “Dissemination and Communication Activities”, which will also identify the internal process of the website updates (i.e., which partners will provide content for the newsletters, which partners will provide information regarding the project activities, its achievements and results, how often the website will be updated with newsletters or news about the project outcomes etc.) Furthermore, possible content updates will be also discussed in the Monthly Project Management Board (PMB) meeting, where the project management team and WP leaders will discuss project developments and decide if there is some interesting material that should be published in the project website and social media.

2.3 Privacy Policy and Cookies Policy

An “Accept Cookies” option is available in the bottom of the ‘Home Page’ when loading the website for the first time (Figure 15) , and options can be modified as shown at any time (Figure 16). This is powered by the WordPress General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Cookie Compliance plugin⁴. The entire policy, which is in alignment with the EU GDPR [5], can be found at the bottom of the ‘Home page’ by clicking on the tab ‘Privacy Policy’ and ‘Terms of Service’. ‘Privacy Policy’, ‘Terms of Service’ and ‘Cookies Policy’ of the website are publicly available in the following URLs and accessible from the Home page:

- Privacy Policy: <https://www.vital5g.eu/privacy-policy/>
- Terms of Service: <https://www.vital5g.eu/terms-of-service/>
- Cookies Policy: <https://www.vital5g.eu/cookies-policy/>

Figure 15: VITAL-5G Website – Accept Cookies

Figure 16: VITAL-5G Website – Change Cookie Settings

⁴ <https://wordpress.org/plugins/gdpr-cookie-compliance/>

2.4 Google Analytics Website Traffic

Google Analytics⁵ is a free web analytics service offered by Google that tracks website traffic and reports a variety of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) offering interesting insights about the website performance. VITAL-5G website is registered in Google Analytics which offers a vast number of reports to satisfy even the more demanding web masters. Figure 17 Figure 18 provide a sample screenshot of the VITAL-5G Google Analytics, where a range of KPIs and overview information, as generated during the first month of the project, are presented, such as:

- Number of sessions, users and page views.
- Unique website visitors, Average session duration and pages viewed per session.
- Users' activity (in the last 30 minutes, real-time, by time of day, etc.).
- Website visitor Sources.
- Users' activity over time and by cohort.
- Demographic statistics (e.g., sessions per country);
- Popularity of website posts.

Updated website “traffic” and more detailed analytics can be presented in future deliverables related to Dissemination and Communication activities, namely D6.2, D6.3 and D6.4, that will be submitted on M5, M18 and M36 respectively.

Figure 17: VITAL-5G Google Analytics (1/2)

⁵ <https://analytics.google.com>

Figure 18: VITAL-5G Google Analytics (2/2)

Close monitoring based on these analytical tools, will be used to improve the overall website’s efficiency and maximise the project’s impact. Monitoring the project’s metrics provides a good overview of the visitors of the website and the project’s social media, along with visitors’ background, industry, interests etc. and the reach the project has achieved. Based on the results, the communication mix i.e., the channels project reaches out to, the kind of material it disseminates (posts, articles, newsletters) can easily be adjusted to reflect the current interest levels and achieve improvements i.e., get a certain industry’s interest if metrics show low participation with the publication of a customized /targeted post to trigger interest. In that way the project proactively reaches its maximum exposure and increase brand awareness.

2.5 Website Administration

This chapter describes the administration site of the project's website. The website has been built using WordPress⁶ (version 5.4.2). WordPress is a web-based software widely used for website designs with emphasis on accessibility, performance, security, and ease of use. WordPress is GDPR compliant and offers a large database of plugins to be used which are always updated with new trends and they are user friendly. The WordPress platform is hosted by Bluehost⁷, a web hosting solutions provider. Bluehost always installs the latest version of WordPress so that all the recent features are available in VITAL-5G website. Using the WordPress, the administrator can create a new page, rename or delete an existing page along with the option to change the content of an existing page. The administrator may also see and edit the whole website interface and structure.

⁶ <https://wordpress.org/about/>

⁷ <https://www.bluehost.com/about>

3 Social Media Channels

This Chapter describes VITAL-5G social media accounts in LinkedIn and Twitter which are (along with the website) part of the dissemination activities undertaken for this project. It was decided by the Consortium that Facebook is not an appropriate social media channel to reach our intended target audience, that’s why we will not have it as part of the dissemination channels.

3.1 VITAL-5G LinkedIn account

The VITAL-5G LinkedIn page <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vital-5g-project/> was created during the first month of the Project. The LinkedIn group provides a large dissemination channel where researchers, and stakeholders in the field of 5G technology can connect and interact with our project. This channel will be used to massively disseminate project facts, results, links to work, links to events etc., including all major project steps, meetings and major outcomes. During the preparation of this report (M2), the group already consisted of 37 followers, and a number of Discussions and announcements. Sample screenshots from the LinkedIn group are presented in Figure 19.

Figure 19: VITAL-5G LinkedIn Page

3.2 VITAL-5G Twitter account

The VITAL-5G Twitter account has also been created since the very early stages of the project (M1) and will be used in a similar approach and dissemination purposes as the LinkedIn group. The scope here is not only to use it as a mass-dissemination tool, but also to provide links between the project partners and related research, stakeholders or potential VITAL-5G solutions up-takers. Twitter will be also maintained throughout the whole project duration. The VITAL-5G Twitter account can be found in the link <https://twitter.com/5gVital>. A sample screenshot from the Twitter group is presented in Figure 20.

Figure 20: VITAL-5G Twitter Page

3.3 VITAL-5G YouTube account

Finally, the VITAL-5G YouTube Channel has already been created and will be used for posting videos related to the project and its outputs, showcasing the upgrades of its testbeds, as well as clips from the executed trials. VITAL-5G YouTube channel is accessible via the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYVsDTKWFAhijxyTZ5H3Uwg>. A snapshot of VITAL-5G YouTube channel is presented in Figure 21.

Figure 21: VITAL-5G YouTube Page

4 Conclusions

This document describes the project's website which is considered as the online VITAL-5G project presence and the associated visuals within the social media channels created for the project following a common structure, colour template and content.

Links to access the website as well as the LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter accounts of the project are also provided within this document. Additionally, the document provides also information regarding the administration of the website, along with the methodology behind the design and development of the website and some statistical reports on website traffic (extracted from Google Analytics).

This deliverable is part of *Task 6.1: Dissemination and Communication activities* performed under *WP6: Dissemination, Communication and Standardization*. For that reason, the content of the website will be continuously updated with dissemination material until the completion of the Project.

Updated website information (i.e., updated screenshots showing events, news, website traffic and more detailed analytics will be presented in the future deliverables of Dissemination and Communication activities, namely D6.2, D6.3 and D6.4, that will be submitted on M5, M18 and M36 respectively.

5 References

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